

Commentary

Nikolsky's Sign: A Commentary on its Clinical Significance

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ABSTRACT

Nikolsky's sign is a clinical dermatological maneuver that dates back more than 2 centuries ago and is named after Pyotr Nikolsky (1858-1940). It has served as a very important diagnostic tool, being pathognomonic for diseases such as pemphigus vulgaris, toxic epidermal necrolysis, and staphylococcal scalded skin syndrome. Nikolsky's sign, however, suffers from a lack of standardization, especially with regards to the method used to elicit the sign. This reduces its standard to be more qualitative than quantitative. Although Nikolsky's sign has a high specificity, it has only a moderate sensitivity of 38% for the diagnosis of Pemphigus Vulgaris. The role of Microscopic Nikolsky's sign has also been discussed as being a better metric than Nikolsky's sign in the diagnosis of PV. In this paper, we discuss the clinical significance of Nikolsky's sign, and the requirement for alternative techniques and manoeuvres.

Keywords: Nikolsky's sign, Microscopic Nikolsky's sign, Pemphigus Vulgaris, Toxic epidermal

Introduction

Nikolsky's sign is a clinical dermatological maneuver that dates back more than 2 centuries ago and is named after Pyotr Nikolsky (1858-1940). Having served as a highly useful diagnostic tool, it has helped diagnose diseases such as pemphigus vulgaris (PV), toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN), and staphylococcal scalded skin syndrome (SSSS).¹ A positive Nikolsky's sign can help distinguish acute dermatoses such as

erythema multiforme from Stevens-Johnson syndrome (SJS) and TEN.²

Nikolsky's sign is elicited by the application of pressure to the external edge of an intact blister, causing the normal epidermis to loosen and the blister to expand. The expansion occurs due to an epidermis being pushed from below by an upward force that is elicited by the application of pressure on the affected area, the area around the affected area, or the normal area.³ The shearing of the very

thin layer of skin, leaving behind pink, moist, and very tender skin is indicative of a positive Nikolsky's sign. Pseudo Nikolsky's sign refers to skin peeling caused by erythematous areas only.⁴

There are several different types of Nikolsky's signs, including 'wet', 'dry', 'marginal', and 'microscopic'.¹ Upon pressing the skin, a wet, glistening, and eroded base is visible. The dry base of eroded skin characterises the dry Nikolsky's sign. The erosion of perilesional skin is characteristic for "marginal Nikolsky's sign", whereas the erosion of normal skin distant from the lesions alludes towards a "direct Nikolsky's sign". "Microscopic Nikolsky's sign" refers to the production of micro morphologies when a tangentially directed pressure is applied to the epidermis.¹

Medical practitioners around the world continue to find this sign extremely valuable since it helps in diagnosing a wide range of threatening diseases in a very simple way. Consequently, treatment and supportive care can be initiated quickly. Diagnosticians around the globe have benefited greatly from its clinical utility in the diagnosis of pemphigus, SSSS, and Lyell's disease. It is useful for discerning between pemphigus vulgaris where it is present from bullous pemphigoid where it is absent. An active acantholytic process and weakening of the epidermis is suggested by the Nikolsky's sign, thus allowing a physician to clearly distinguish between intraepidermal and sub epidermal blistering. Additionally, it is indicative of the prognosis of the disease indicating if the disease is active or if it has exacerbated² and is of great use in regions that lack immunofluorescence facilities.⁵

Is there any evidence suggestive of Nikolsky's sign being outdated?

Nikolsky's sign, however, suffers from a lack of standardization, especially with regards to the

method used to elicit the sign. This reduces its standard to be more qualitative than quantitative. Although Nikolsky's sign has a high specificity, it has only a moderate sensitivity of 38% for the diagnosis of PV.⁶ A study reported an incidence frequency of 11.1% for positive clinical Nikolsky's sign in PV and remarked on the role of the low sensitivity in the difficulty in the establishment of a diagnosis of PV in some patients.⁷

Microscopic Nikolsky's sign was also considered to be a superior metric than Nikolsky's sign in diagnosing PV.⁷ Upon the application of tangential pressure to the skin or mucosa, the pathological changes induced are referred to as microscopic Nikolsky's sign, and this sign has been found to be an accurate and sensitive method in the diagnosis of various disorders with great rapidity.⁷ Thus it served great purpose in health care centres where immunofluorescence techniques are unavailable.⁸

In contrast, Nikolsky's sign does not relate to the degree of skin splitting and is found in only a small number of partially treated patients.⁸ Therefore, in cases of weakening of intracellular adhesion, but not marked damage, only microscopic examination can reveal the injury.

It has been observed that in generalized disease, the presence of microscopic Nikolsky's sign is due to the presence of higher pemphigus antibody levels.⁷

Is Nikolsky's sign reliable and sufficient as it is?

The low sensitivity of Nikolsky's sign has always been raised as a counter to its clinical efficacy. However, the technique appears to be very specific to the oral setting (96.3%), making it useful for diagnosing oral blisters.⁹ It is pathognomonic for PV and helps differentiate intradermal blistering diseases from subdermal blistering diseases.⁴ It is a very simple maneuver to perform and helps in the early diagnosis of cases of PV, which is absolutely

vital in the treatment and management of PV, as it can progress quickly, and become life-threatening. Its importance in the early detection of mucous membrane pemphigoid and pemphigus vulgaris has also been well documented, where it was reported with a 97.4 % accuracy.⁹

If performed correctly, Nikolsky's sign can be a very valuable asset in assisting in the early diagnosis of pemphigus,² and other potentially lethal mucocutaneous diseases and it has been recommended that every clinician should become adept in the recognition and interpretation of these signs.⁹

Conclusion

Despite its early origin more than two centuries ago, Nikolsky's sign remains an important tool in medicine throughout the world, helping to diagnose a wide range of potentially serious conditions at a glance, and it remains a major asset to the profession even today.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Maity S, Banerjee I, Sinha R, Jha H, Ghosh P, Mustafi S. Nikolsky's sign: A pathognomic boon. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2020;9(2):526-530. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_889_19, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7114071/>
2. Shah A, Roberts E, Engelina S, Carras E. The Nikolsky sign. *British Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2018 ;79(9):142-144. doi: 10.12968/hmed.2018.79.9.
3. Sachdev D. Sign of Nikolskiy & related signs. *Indian Journal of Dermatology Venereology and Leprology*. 2003 ;69(3):243-244. <https://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/html/1807/24024/dv03018.html>.
4. Soni AG. Nikolsky's sign-A clinical method to evaluate damage at epidermal-dermal junction. *Journal of Indian Academy of Oral Medicine and Radiology*. 2018;30(1):68-72. DOI:10.4103/jiaomr.jiaomr_95_17, <https://www.jiaomr.in/article.asp?issn=0972-1363;year=2018;volume=30;issue=1;spage=68;epage=72;aulast=Soni>.
5. Salopek TG. Nikolsky's sign: is it 'dry' or is it 'wet'?. *British Journal of Dermatology*. 1997 ;136(5):762-767. doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2133.1997.6711627.x, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1046/j.1365-2133.1997.6711627.x>
6. Uzun S, Durdu M. The specificity and sensitivity of Nikolskiy sign in the diagnosis of pemphigus. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*. 2006;54(3):411-415. doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2005.10.019, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0190962205032524>
7. Barzegari M, Valikhani M, Esmaili N, Naraghi Z, Nikoo A, Kamyab K, et al. Microscopic Nikolsky's sign: Is it useful for diagnosis of pemphigus vulgaris? *Iranian Journal of Dermatology*. 2008;11(2):64-66. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=126226>
8. Hameed A, Khan AA. Microscopic Nikolsky's sign. *Clinical and experimental dermatology*.1999 ;24(4):312-314. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2230.1999.00487.x, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1046/j.1365-2230.1999.00487.x>

9. Mignogna MD, Fortuna G, Leuci S, Ruoppo E, Marasca F, Matarasso S. Nikolsky's sign on the gingival mucosa: a clinical tool for oral health practitioners. *Journal of Periodontology*. 2008;79(12):2241-2246. doi.org/10.1902/jop.2008.080217. <http://aap.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1902/jop.2008.080217>

Contributions of the Authors

AAR Conceptualized the Study, Designed the Study, Contributed to the first draft, and edited the final version of the manuscript

AJ Helped design the Study, Contributed to the first draft, and edited the final version of the manuscript

